

INDIVIDUAL WORK WITH EACH STUDENT IS THE KEY TO SUCCESS IN THE WORK OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20626698>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 02nd June 2026

Accepted: 09th June 2026

Online: 10th June 2026

KEYWORDS

Individual work, lifting by force, high crossbar, hanging on bent arms, long-term planning.

ABSTRACT

The article states that individual work in physical education lessons with each student is one of the modern aspects of the work of a physical education teacher in a lesson. Working with each student is a perspective that a teacher should have. It should be implemented starting with the development of individual plans for the growth of physical fitness of students according to a number of indicators.

Individual work in physical education classes with each student is one of the modern aspects of a physical education teacher's role. Many of our teachers today are seeking ways to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process in general education schools, ensuring that classes are conducted at a high level. One approach that seems promising is the planning of individual work aimed at developing students' motor skills and, based on this, forming higher-order motor skills.

Of course, it is impossible to achieve this objective without creating acceptable optimal conditions for physical education, allowing each student to systematically develop their motor abilities and achieve maximum results in competition with their peers at all stages of learning. Thus, a plan for the development and improvement of the material and technical base for physical education can be outlined, taking into account all the possibilities of the school and the physical education teacher.

The strategy of working with each student is one that the teacher should embrace. Implementing this requires starting with the development of individual plans for improving students' physical fitness based on various indicators. This should include all the educational standards prescribed by the program, along with several additional ones that significantly broaden each student's physical fitness potential.

To develop and create individual plans that take into account the age and morphological characteristics of children, as well as their personal interest in physical exercise, collaboration between educators in pedagogy and physiology is essential.

The starting benchmarks should be the previously achieved indicators found in the "Alpomish" and "Barchina" standards. The targeted outcome logically follows from the realistic capabilities of the student as well as from the individual program that is intended during the physical training process.

For instance, when planning results in cross-country training, it is necessary to approach goals with the highest standards, based on the relatively high preparedness of students in these sections of the curriculum. Conversely, when planning results in short-distance running or high jumps, the main objective should be the growth of individual indicators, regardless of the assessment standards.

The teacher must also consider other factors. For example, during the summer holidays, most students do not engage in physical exercise systematically. It is therefore necessary to plan for a real decline in performance indicators at the beginning of the upcoming academic year, which indeed occurs. For instance, practice shows that a student who completed 10-12 pull-ups at the end of the academic year would only manage 6-8 pull-ups in the first classes at the beginning of the new academic year, and typically only reached their previous results by the end of the first quarter. This situation necessitates smartly creating the prerequisites for performance improvement, which primarily manifests in the volume of training exercises. The volume of tasks reflects growth dynamics, which can be more pronounced for some students and less intense for others.

For physically fit students who enjoy engaging in physical exercises and participate in sports sections, higher performance indicators are planned, often exceeding the limits set by the established educational standards. For instance, a student engaged in a sports section who achieves the best result in pull-ups of 12-14 repetitions should,

after an individual discussion, be set the goal of performing 18-20 pull-ups. This agreed-upon foundation forms the basis for the individual education program, which can include exercises such as muscle-ups on a high bar, backward rolls from a support, and holding a hang on bent arms for a certain period, gradually transitioning to one arm. By the end of the training, the student should fully implement their plan, even exceeding it. Throughout the academic year, all planned results-developed with the input of every student in the fall-are then discussed and clarified, and sometimes amendments are made based on suggestions from students during individual conversations.

All information about this extensive and complex work is displayed on the physical fitness screen. Typically, it is necessary to note only the growth of results in comparison to the initial data. For this purpose, space is left in each column dedicated to a specific motor skill or assessment exercise to subsequently record 4-8 results. The teacher must maintain a working journal to track and monitor the progress of students' motor skills, abilities, and competencies, which includes their completion of additional assignments, exercises, and tests. The physical fitness screen, which will include the names of all students by class, serves as a school-wide working board with systematically updated information. Its materials attract the attention of students, who study and analyze their results in comparison with others. The screen allows class leaders, all educators, and, of course, parents to see how students manage their individual physical self-improvement programs.

It should be noted that when implementing personalized plans, the time allocated for active physical activity is considered within the school's daily routine. The majority of controlled exercises aimed at developing motor skills are included in the teacher's annual planning, where nearly every lesson features an assessment of a particular motor skill, systematically repeated every few lessons. The time spent on most controlled exercises does not exceed 2-4 minutes, achieved through the use of an increased number of non-standard equipment.

This leads to a closer interaction between the teacher and the student, which occurs in a relaxed setting during individual discussions. The daily analysis of each student's actions while recording controlled exercises provides a deeper understanding than the general analysis, which now merely complements the initial one.

Students in the younger grades happily report their personal best results, while high school students may express a sense of inadequacy, saying, "I think I'm not doing so well." Together, it's important to seek the reason behind this. In most cases, there should be no limit on the number of attempts during controlled exercises. For example, in the long jump, the best result is not based on 3 attempts but rather on 5-6 attempts. Pull-ups can be repeated twice in a single session, and multiple throws can be conducted within a lesson. The same goes for jumping over a vaulting horse, which students can attempt at greater heights without restrictions based on their mastery of the motor skill.

The result of any educational activity serves as a significant motivator and driving force for both the student and the teacher. When the process of physical education is well integrated into a cohesive chain of intermediate results, achieving the final goal is unquestionable.

The teacher's constant interest in the success of each individual student elicits a positive response. Students, including those who are weaker or exempt from certain exercises due to various challenges, are motivated to push themselves, not wanting to fall behind their peers.

In their work, teachers must constantly maintain communication with the parents of their students, as well as with the school physician and the treating physician. For students for whom certain exercises are contraindicated based on the doctor's assessment, it's necessary to recommend focusing solely on the qualitative execution of motor skills. Some students may experience dizziness when performing forward rolls. Instead of rolls, these students can be offered exercises to improve vestibular function that are easier to perform at their current stage of physical development. Only later, after several months or even years of building a foundation of conditioning, will they be able to learn the forward roll.

As we can see, the task of planning also involves finding forms for its implementation in an individual context. Long-term planning for students in the main medical group is reflected in the earlier inclusion of additional exercises that are typical for high school students into the middle and elementary school

levels, which promotes gradual accessibility in learning, as opposed to the acceleration that sometimes occurs. To achieve this, extra and auxiliary exercises should be incorporated into skill development.

In practice, there should be a balance between mandatory exercises and the free choice of additional exercises. For example, if a student completes a high jump at the learning stage using a low bar, it is advisable to provide 2-3 exercises for developing jumping ability. For those who have successfully completed the tasks of a particular lesson, specific exercises should be selected to develop certain muscle groups.

A physical education teacher must not only be well aware of today's demands of their students but also be able to foresee the prospects for future work. What is the outlook for homework assignments? Unfortunately, years of experience with the conventional system of homework assignments have confirmed some of its inefficiencies. Only a small percentage of students consistently complete the assigned exercises, and quality is no longer in question. By exchanging experiences, it can be concluded that success is achieved only by those educators who have managed to "connect" with the students, taking on most of the monitoring responsibility.

To address this, goals should be developed with a long-term perspective tailored to each individual student, while preserving interaction methods that yield the most effective results. Goals should be realistic and achievable, yet simultaneously high and challenging.

Without specialized and independent work, as well as additional training, achieving these goals becomes impossible. In this context, the student actively seeks out the teacher for homework assignments, intending to complete them in their sports section, at home, or at the stadium.

Students appreciate this long-term planning of their physical development, where higher goals are set for them each year. What seemed unattainable yesterday is already becoming the norm today. Previously "quiet" students who didn't stand out are transforming and showing excellent results.

In this environment, the common set of exercises assigned as homework gains new significance. Additionally, individual assignments focusing on a student's favorite exercise draw primary attention and again contribute to improving overall physical fitness.

New supplementary exercises and tasks require various forms of interaction between the teacher and the students. Task cards are a valuable tool in this regard. Each card includes the initial and target results, as well as options for performing the exercises. When a student reaches the final target result, they submit their previous card, which can be reused, and upon request, they receive a new one.

During the lesson, task cards are handed out to groups of students (2-5 students) with similar levels of physical development. The exercises selected for them should be varied and non-repetitive. Sometimes the class performs as many as 40-50 exercises simultaneously. In the next lesson, the exercises for the groups are changed. The

high level of activity is attributed to the novelty of the motor tasks and the opportunity to showcase oneself by completing the assigned tasks. The teacher, engaging with students individually, assists in the quality execution of exercises and conducts the necessary planned assessments.

While paying considerable attention to the group teaching method during the lesson, which allows for the effective use of individual assignments, it is essential to conduct psychological and pedagogical testing of students for compatibility during lessons and training sessions. The application of this method enhances productivity and helps mitigate negative reactions among students during group activities.

Thus, exercises in pairs are consistently performed by two classmates who have a positive relationship with each other and enjoy working with their partner, providing mutual support. In groups, the percentage of compatibility is somewhat lower; a composition of 3-5 individuals is optimal in this scenario. With such consistent groups (lasting a year or more), formed according to the number of students (depending on the lesson's objectives), undesirable phenomena in collective learning are almost completely eliminated. This also saves time on additional restructuring, promoting greater self-organization among students.

At the same time, it is essential to create temporary divisions during specific lessons, selecting students based on their mastery of motor skills. Accordingly, each division receives its own assignment with varying levels of

difficulty. As the motor skill is mastered, the teacher plans immediate transitions for students from one division to another for completing more challenging tasks. This way, there is a continuous increase in physical fitness and the development of motor skills individually for each student at different stages of learning. One student may be only preparing to master a motor skill, while another in a different division may already be refining that skill.

When consolidating basketball skills, it is necessary to form balanced teams with players of similar capabilities. Utilizing more prepared players to take on leadership roles and assist girls in mixed teams is beneficial. Again, it is essential to consider both personal connections (the degree of compatibility determined through previous pedagogical observations and research) and other relevant factors such as mood for the game and the level of engagement of the participants.

In track and field events, alongside the mastery of motor skills, it is crucial to plan for each lesson interim assessments of standards and the number of repetitions for both preparatory and main exercises. While working individually with each student, adjustments and modifications should be made, keeping notes in the working journal. Undoubtedly, it is easier to select individual exercises and loads for their execution based on students' interests than to create the necessary conditions for their implementation. Without establishing a proper educational and material base in schools, it is impossible to fundamentally improve the quality of student training. Each teacher, in their

practice of enhancing the school's sports infrastructure, should plan for the long term and for each academic year. This includes preparing simple sports equipment and training devices.

By applying and implementing individual planning for students' physical development in school during

the first academic year, it is possible to significantly increase their physical fitness indicators. In the second year, we believe that the growth in physical fitness indicators will continue, not just for individual students, but for a significant portion of those engaged, surpassing the academic standards.

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